

DISCLAIMER

Re: "Night Shift: Overnight Drift Anomaly in Small-Cap ETFs"— Fernando Arruda de Faria

1. Educational and Research Purpose Only

This paper, including all associated code, data, charts, tables, backtests, and commentary (collectively, the "Materials"), is published solely for educational, academic, and research purposes. The Materials document a quantitative research exercise and are intended to contribute to public discussion of market microstructure, anomaly research, and the methodological challenges of out-of-sample testing.

2. Not Investment Advice

Nothing in the Materials constitutes investment advice, financial advice, trading advice, tax advice, legal advice, or a recommendation to buy, sell, hold, or transact in any security, derivative, ETF, fund, or other financial instrument. The author is not a registered investment adviser, broker-dealer, financial planner, or fiduciary in any jurisdiction. The Materials are not personalized to any reader's financial situation, risk tolerance, time horizon, tax position, or investment objectives.

3. No Solicitation, No Offer

The Materials do not constitute an offer to sell or a solicitation of an offer to buy any security or financial product. They are not directed at any person in any jurisdiction where such distribution would be unlawful.

4. Past Performance and Backtested Results

All performance figures presented — including but not limited to Sharpe ratios, drawdowns, returns, and out-of-sample statistics — are derived from historical data and backtested simulations. **Backtested performance is hypothetical, does not represent actual trading, and is subject to well-documented biases including but not limited to: data-snooping, survivorship bias, look-ahead bias, regime dependency, transaction cost mis-specification, market impact, slippage, borrow availability, liquidity constraints, and the absence of behavioral and emotional factors that affect live execution.** Past performance is not indicative of future results. No representation is made that any account will or is likely to achieve results similar to those shown.

5. Risk of Loss

Trading equities, ETFs, and derivatives involves substantial risk of loss, including the risk of total loss of capital. Strategies that perform well in historical samples may underperform, fail, or

produce catastrophic losses in live deployment. Readers who choose to act on any idea, framework, or signal contained in the Materials do so entirely at their own risk and on their own independent judgment.

6. No Liability

The author expressly disclaims any and all liability for any direct, indirect, incidental, consequential, special, or exemplary damages arising from any use of, or reliance on, the Materials. Without limiting the foregoing, the author is not responsible for any trading losses, opportunity costs, tax consequences, or other harms incurred by any reader who implements, adapts, or attempts to implement any strategy described herein.

7. Independent Judgment Required

Readers are strongly encouraged to consult a qualified, licensed financial professional before making any investment decision. Any reader who chooses to deploy capital based on concepts in the Materials assumes full and exclusive responsibility for that decision and its consequences.

8. Accuracy and Completeness

While reasonable care has been taken in preparing the Materials, the author makes no representation or warranty, express or implied, regarding their accuracy, completeness, timeliness, or suitability for any particular purpose. Data may contain errors. Code may contain bugs. Conclusions may be wrong.

9. No Inducement, No Conflict Disclosed Beyond This Document

The author may or may not, at any time, hold positions in the instruments referenced in the Materials. The Materials are not produced in exchange for compensation from any issuer, fund sponsor, or counterparty.

10. Jurisdiction

This disclaimer is intended to apply to readers in all jurisdictions and shall be construed as broadly as permissible under applicable law. If any provision is found unenforceable, the remaining provisions shall remain in full force.

Fernando Arruda de Faria